

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 4.2 Input from national governments on the focus and outputs from the project

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

Collective view

This document has been prepared on behalf of the Zero Emissions Platform Advisory Council and the SET-Plan Implementation Plan working group on CCUS (IWG9) Plenary. Views and opinions expressed are the collective views of the Advisory Council and the Plenary, not of individual members or participants

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Contact details:

+32 2 882 50 07

iwg9@zeroemissionsplatform.eu

www.ccus-setplan.eu

www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement 101075790

1 INTRODUCTION

D4.2 Input from national governments on the focus and outputs from the project.

The deliverable contains information regarding the Member States contributions on the orientation and focus of the project.

1.1 Role of the Government Group

The Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) hosts a Government Group, which was set up as a place for collaboration between European Government stakeholders and the European Commission (DG ENER, DG CLIMA, and DG RTD).

The group has increased strongly over the last years and includes representatives from 23 Member State Governments active or interested in CCS and CCU, meeting quarterly to mutually exchange on national CCS/CCU developments, as well as representatives from the European Commission.

These representatives typically include civil servants working on CCS/CCU in ministries or public organisations. The meetings are closed to representatives from non-public organisations. This rule helps foster open discussions on various topics of relevance at the national level. Presentations by external stakeholders are authorised.

The group has the following core objectives:

- Support national governments by collecting and disseminating information.
- Ensure an effective liaison between the European Commission and national governments.
- Ensure an effective liaison between industry and national governments.

With several countries preparing national strategies for CCS and CCU and an increasing number of ongoing and planned projects across Europe, the Government Group is also crucial in the coordination between EU and national strategies, policies, and funding opportunities.

The Government Group also actively fed into the preparation of ZEP's work programme for 2022-2023, making sure that the priorities for the Platform reflected Member States own priorities. The Government Group is the key interface between ZEP's work and the national governments. ZEP's position on various policy files can be presented at the Government Group.

Government Group meetings are well attended; 27 representatives participated in the latest meeting in March 2024. Hybrid meetings are also successful. Meetings in Copenhagen and Berlin in 2023 allowed for information exchange and personal contacts between government representatives, which facilitates and supports international cooperation. Site visits also allow for a direct exchange between project developers and policymakers.

1.2 Feedback on the Projects Network

The Zero Emissions Platform with Porthos organised the first edition of the Projects Network in Rotterdam on 24 and 25 January 2024. The meeting gathered over 120 delegates from across 17 European countries. About 80% of participants said they were involved in a CCS project (commercial scale or pilot). Sessions were allowed to provide feedback and learning from the Porthos project to other CCS project developers and managers. The key takeaways of the sessions were noted down by participants on flip charts and shared with participants after the meeting. The recommendations from this first edition are currently under review and will be shared with participants and policymakers when available.

The Projects Network is intended to provide on-the-ground recommendations from projects to the Government Group to facilitate the deployment of projects and address identified on-the-ground problems.

One government representative attended the first edition in Rotterdam. This representative gave very positive feedback on the functioning of the Projects Network during the Government Group meeting in March 2024.

2 GOVERNMENT GROUP MEETINGS DURING THE GRANT PERIOD

Since the start of the grant period in July 2022, the Government Group met 8 times:

- 4 October 2022
- 6 December 2022
- 7 March 2023
- 28 June 2023
- 4 October 2023
- 14 November 2023
- 7 March 2024
- 6 June 2024

Meeting agendas can be found under Annex 1.

3 SURVEY

3.1 Initial survey

A survey was sent to Government Group participants to gather feedback on the role of ZEP and the IWG9 and possibilities to improve their work under the SET Plan. The survey was anonymised to create confidence and ensure a sufficient level of response. This survey aims to receive input to improve the role of ZEP and the IWG9.

This survey was sent on 17 May 2024 to all members of the Government Group. 5 respondents provided input via this survey. This survey was complemented by a phone survey with 4 additional respondents. In general, there is consistency and direction in the responses provided. The 9 respondents provided fairly consistent and informative feedback, even though the results cannot be considered statistically significant. The full online survey responses can be found under Annex 2.

If the online and phone surveys are taken together (*see below*), 11% of respondents state that ZEP has a neutral impact for the progress of the SET Plan, while 67% of respondents state that ZEP has a significant impact. 22% of respondents state that ZEP has a very significant impact. None indicate a low or very low impact.

All online respondents provide positive feedback on the quality of the outputs produced by ZEP. This feedback includes the following details:

- “ZEP plays a role in highlighting future challenges and avoid hidden problems”
- “Government Group meetings are very informative and useful”
- “ZEP’s work is good”
- “Theoretical/abstract work due to the fact the CCS not yet operational at large scale”
- “Very good work”
- “High-quality work”

Online feedback on the possibilities to improve ZEP included the following elements:

- “Consider synergies with hydrogen (understood as broadening the scope to the blending of hydrogen and CO₂ to produce methanol and to low-carbon ‘blue’ hydrogen)”
- “Information sharing about problems or failures of CO₂ storage sites”
- “Information sharing when projects take final investment decisions and/or become operational”

Online feedback on the future topics of focus for ZEP included the following elements:

- “Consider synergies with hydrogen (understood as broadening the scope to the blending of hydrogen and CO₂ to produce methanol and to low-carbon ‘blue’ hydrogen)”
- “Providing solutions to improve public acceptance and ensuring adequate coordination of actors along the value chain”
- “Information sharing when projects take final investment decisions and/or become operational”

If the online and phone surveys are taken together (*see below*), 50% of respondents state that the IWG9 has a neutral impact for the progress of the SET Plan. 33% of respondents see a significant impact. 17% of respondents see a very significant impact.

All online respondents provided positive feedback on the quality of the outputs produced by the IWG9. This feedback includes the following details:

- “Satisfactory”
- “Very good”
- “Facilitates the deployment of CCS”

Online feedback on the possibilities to improve the IWG9 included the following elements:

- “Consider synergies with hydrogen (understood as broadening the scope to the blending of hydrogen and CO₂ to produce methanol and to low-carbon ‘blue’ hydrogen)”

Online feedback on the future topics of focus for the IWG9 included the following elements:

- “Consider synergies with hydrogen (understood as broadening the scope to the blending of hydrogen and CO₂ to produce methanol and to low-carbon ‘blue’ hydrogen)”
- “Focusing on projects taking final investment decisions and/or becoming operational”

Online feedback on the possibility for the SET Plan to contribute to national policy included the following elements:

- “Liaising with national policymakers and creating common events”
- “Communication with national contact points”

Online feedback on the possibility of being more included in the SET Plan in the future included the following elements:

- “Positive response”
- “Already involved”

Online feedback to improve the relevance of the SET Plan at the national level included the following elements:

- “Extending the range of issues to cover financial incentives”
- “Focusing on practical information and data once projects become operational and investments are taken”

3.2 Additional phone survey

A phone survey complemented this initial survey to increase the overall responses and ensure decent representativity. Government Group participants were called over the phone and asked questions from the online survey.

Responses to the phone survey can be found below:

Regarding the progress of the SET Plan, do you consider that ZEP has:

- *Respondent 1: A neutral impact*
- *Respondent 2: A significant impact*
- *Respondent 3: A significant impact*
- *Respondent 4: A very significant impact*

What is your view on the quality of the outputs produced under the Zero Emissions Platform?

- *Respondent 1: Very good, very good work*
- *Respondent 2: Very good quality*
- *Respondent 3: High quality*
- *Respondent 4: Very good, I am deeply involved*

In what areas could ZEP be improved?

- *Respondent 1: There could be more emphasis on in-person exchanges, emulating the Government Group in-person site visit that took place in Copenhagen last year.*
- *Respondent 2: No response*
- *Respondent 3: No response*
- *Respondent 4: No response*

What work should ZEP focus on in the future?

- *Respondent 1: Stronger focus on North Sea infrastructure and infrastructure shared between countries*
- *Respondent 2: The upcoming regulatory framework on transport and storage*
- *Respondent 3: Participation in the Government Group is useful, especially for the national updates. Having a forum on upcoming new regulations is important*
- *Respondent 4: Foster a political environment that is supportive of CCS, active governments are needed*

Regarding the progress of the SET Plan, do you consider that the IWG9 has:

- *Respondent 1: Don't know*

- *Respondent 2: Don't know*
- *Respondent 3: No response*
- *Respondent 4: A neutral impact*

What is your view on the quality of the outputs produced under the IWG9?

- *Respondent 1: Don't know*
- *Respondent 2: High quality*
- *Respondent 3: High quality*
- *Respondent 4: Moderate*

In what areas could the IWG9 be improved?

- *Respondent 1: Don't know*
- *Respondent 2: Not sure*
- *Respondent 3: No opinion, not participating*
- *Respondent 4: By fostering a political environment that is supportive of CCS, active governments are needed*

What work should the IWG9 focus on in the future?

- *Respondent 1: Don't know*
- *Respondent 2: Not sure*
- *Respondent 3: Don't know*
- *Respondent 4: Fostering a political environment that is supportive of CCS, active governments are needed*

How could the SET Plan contribute further to national policies and developments?

- *Respondent 1: By connecting R&I efforts directly to researchers and by getting input from researchers*
- *Respondent 2: By producing relevant outputs that are directly applicable at the national level*
- *Respondent 3: Already very useful, latest CCS developments are useful to know about, work can continue the way it is (eg Government Group)*
- *Respondent 4: By fostering a political environment that is supportive of CCS, active governments are needed*

Would you like to be more involved in the SET Plan in the future? In what way?

- *Respondent 1: Yes, there is value in getting further involved in R&I as Scotland*
- *Respondent 2: Involvement in the Government Group is already quite good*

- *Respondent 3: It's a question of resources at the national level. I would like to but it's not guaranteed*
- *Respondent 4: Yes, I would like to be more involved*

How could the SET Plan/IWG9 be more relevant to national governments?

- *Respondent 1: By including the regional level*
- *Respondent 2: Don't know*
- *Respondent 3: Enabling fora, such as the Government Group, where countries can engage with each other*
- *Respondent 4: By organising in all countries local meetings for people interested in CCS. This would help inform people, create local debate, and allow to feel the local pulse. These meetings should take place with experienced specialists and local authorities.*

This additional phone survey confirms the quality of the outputs but also appears to indicate a lack of awareness about the IWG9. This is shown by the lack of precise responses for some questions related to the IWG9. This trend has been identified throughout the project and efforts have been made to explain the role of the IWG9 under the SET Plan, especially during the revision process of the R&I targets and activities. This suggests that further efforts are possible to increase the visibility of the IWG9. Feedback from the Government Group, and general ZEP work, appears to be positive.

ANNEX 1, GOVERNMENT GROUP MEETING AGENDAS

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 4 October 2022, 10.30 – 15.00 CET

Hybrid meeting (Norway House, 17 rue Archimède Brussels)

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Chair / ZEP Secretariat	10:30 – 10:35
2 Update on ZEP activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recent ZEP activities 	ZEP Secretariat	10:35 – 10:45
3 Denmark's national programme for CCUS Presentation of the national CCUS strategy	Jasmin Sharzad, Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities	10:45 – 11:25
4 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Are you involved in cross-border discussions? Are there bottlenecks and/or enablers you can identify? Are there new CCUS funding opportunities? 	All	11:25 – 12:10
5 Guidance on the draft work programme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP outline work programme 2022-2023 – <i>pre-read 2</i> Are there missing elements in the programme? What would you like to see as focus areas for the next Government Group meetings? 	All	12:10 – 12:40
LUNCH BREAK		12:40 – 13:40
6 How to include more CCUS/CO2 infrastructure in the revised national energy and climate plans? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Will your NECP change regarding CCS and CCU? Will CCS-CCU be included in your strategy? 	All	13:40 - 14:10

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How can ZEP support the EC and European governments for increased CCUS inclusion? 		
7	CCUS Forum <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short updates from the working groups on Vision, CO2 infrastructure and Industrial partnership 	All, ZEP Secretariat	14:10 - 14:40
8	Next meetings Suggested dates for the next meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6 December 2022 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 8 March 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 8 June 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 20 September 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 15 November 2023 (10:30-16:00 – Hybrid) 	ZEP Secretariat	14:40 - 14:55
9	Final remarks and AOB	Chair	14:55 - 15:00

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 6 December 2022, 10.30 – 12.30 CET

Virtual meeting

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Chair / ZEP Secretariat	10:30 - 10:35
2 Update on ZEP activities and EU timeline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recent ZEP activities EU policy and funding timeline 	ZEP Secretariat	10:35 - 10:50
3 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group Members <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update on licensing rounds Update on national CCUS policy, strategy, and funding opportunities 	All	10:50 - 12:00

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EC guidance for the review of the NECPs in 2023 CO2 imports / exports – bilateral agreements and way forward after EC analysis paper 		
4	Guidance on the draft work programme <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP work programme 2023 What would you like to see as focus areas of the Government Group?	ZEP Secretariat, All	12:00 - 12:20
5	Next meetings Suggested dates for the next meetings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8 March 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) 8 June 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) 15 November 2023 (10:30-15:00 – Hybrid) 	ZEP Secretariat	12:20 - 12:25
6	Final remarks and AOB	Chair	12:25 - 12:30

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 7 March 2023, 10.30 – 14.15 CET

Hybrid meeting: Scotland House (Rond-point Robert Schuman 44, 1040 Brussels) and Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> New chair 	Chair	10:30 - 10:40
2 Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group Members updates	All	10:40 - 11:20
3 The CCS4CEE project	Michał Wendolowski (Bellona Europa)	11:20 - 11:50
4 ZEP's response to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body call for feedback	Secretariat, All	11:50 - 12:10

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What should ZEP highlight? 		
LUNCH BREAK			
5	ZEP developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZEP's new Chair • Work Programme • New Network Projects 	ZEP Secretariat	13:00 - 13:20
6	CCS and CCU outlook <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication on a Strategy for CCS and CCU • Green Deal Industrial Plan • How should ZEP engage? What should ZEP highlight? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	13:20 - 13:40
7	Status of CCS in Iceland <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy landscape • Funding and commercial/business models 	Helga Barðadóttir (Ministry of the Environment, Energy and Climate)	13:40 - 14:10
8	Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 June 2023 (10:30-15:00, Copenhagen) • 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00) • 15 November 2023 (10:30-15:00, Berlin) 	Chair, ZEP Secretariat	14:10 - 14:15

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 28 June 2023, 10.30 – 12.30 CEST

Hybrid meeting: Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (Holmens Kanal 20 DK-1060 Copenhagen, Denmark) and Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Jasmin Sharzad (Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities)	10:30 - 10:40
2 New ZEP Network Projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up 	ZEP Secretariat, All	10:40 – 10:55

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possible coordination with Government Group 		
3	Updates on national CCS/CCU developments Roundtable – Government Group member updates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National developments: policy and funding Bilateral agreements National Energy and Climate Plans, ahead of the EU Strategy for CCS and CCU 	All	10:55 – 11:40
4	The Net-Zero Industry Act proposal <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP position – <i>pre-read 2</i> Other points to consider? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	11:40 – 11:55
5	Paris Agreement: carbon removals Article 6.4 mechanism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP responses – <i>pre-reads 3, 4 and 5</i> Future actions? 	ZEP Secretariat, All	11:55 – 12:10
6	CCS updates from the Bonn Climate Change Conference	Stig Sverningsen (Norwegian Ministry of Petroleum and Energy)	12:10 – 12:25
7	Next meeting dates and AOB 20 September 2023 (10:30-15:00) – to be rescheduled 14 November 2023 (10:30-15:00, Berlin)	ZEP Secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 4 October 2023, 10:00 – 12:30 CEST

Online meeting: Microsoft Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	ZEP secretariat	10:00 - 10:10

2	Updates from ZEP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> New ZEP Secretary-General New Projects Network – presentation and coordination with the Government Group 	ZEP secretariat, All	10:10 – 10:20
3	Updates on national CCS and CCU developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roundtable – country updates Policy and funding developments Bilateral agreements 	All	10:20 – 11:15
4	Net Zero Industry Act <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legislative state-of-play – <i>pre-read 2</i> Group discussion: what are your views on the Act? can the Act be finalised before the 2024 European Parliament election? 	ZEP secretariat, All	11:15 – 11:45
5	National Energy and Climate Plans State-of-play and next steps – <i>pre-read 3</i> How will CCS and CCU be included in the updated NECPs?	ZEP secretariat, All	11:45 – 12:05
6	Industrial carbon management strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP’s position – <i>pre-read 4</i> Group discussion: which elements are key for the strategy? 	ZEP secretariat, All	12:05 – 12:25
7	Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 14 November (Berlin) – <i>pre-read 5</i> 	ZEP secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 14 November 2023, 10:00 – 12:00 CEST

Hybrid meeting: Scharnhorststraße 34-37, 10115 Berlin & Microsoft Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
------	----------------	------

1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes of the last meeting – <i>pre-read 1</i> 	Ministry for economic affairs and climate action of Germany (BMWK)	10:00 – 10:10
2 Germany's upcoming strategy on CCS and CCU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation 	Ministry for economic affairs and climate action of Germany (BMWK)	10:10 – 10:30
3 Updates on national CCS and CCU developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roundtable – country updates 	All	10:30 – 11:00
4 Updates from ZEP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Projects Network – presentation and coordination with the Government Group 	Stijn Santen, EBN (tbc)	11:00 – 11:10
5 Net Zero Industry Act and Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legislative state-of-play – <i>pre-read 2</i> Group discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> what are your views on the ENVI report? can the texts be finalised before the 2024 European Parliament election? 	ZEP secretariat, All	11:10 – 11:25
6 European Commission report on the implementation of the CO2 storage directive <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main messages Implication regarding the London Protocol 	DG CLIMA (tbc)	11:25 – 11:35
7 European ports in cross-border CO2 transport (tbc) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UK study 'CCUS Ports – Infrastructure Requirement Assessment' 	UK Department for Energy Security and Net Zero	11:35 – 11:55
8 Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2024 meeting dates 	ZEP secretariat	11:55 – 12:00

ZEP Government Group meeting

Meeting Agenda: 7 March 2024, 10:00 – 12:30 CEST

Online meeting: Microsoft Teams

Item	Lead Presenter	Time
1 Welcome and introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome Approval of draft agenda and draft minutes of the last meeting – <i>pre-read 1</i> Update on ZEP activities 	ZEP secretariat	10:00 – 10:15
2 Key points of Germany's carbon management strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation 	Ministry for economic affairs and climate action of Germany	10:15 – 10:30
3 Updates on national CCS and CCU developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roundtable – country updates 	All	10:30 – 11:00
4 Study 'Shaping the future CO2 transport network for Europe' <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation 	Joint Research Centre	11:00 – 11:15
5 Industrial carbon management strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the strategy 	DG ENER (tbc)	11:15 – 11:35
6 Net Zero Industry Act <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the final compromise text 	DG CLIMA (tbc)	11:35 – 11:55
7 Carbon removal certification framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the provisional agreement 	DG CLIMA (tbc)	11:55 – 12:10
8 Croatia's plan for CCS/CCU (tbc) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation 	Croatian Ministry of Economy, Business and Trade	12:10 – 12:25
9 Next meeting dates and AOB <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2024 meeting dates Proposed September meeting in France 	ZEP secretariat	12:25 – 12:30

ANNEX 2, SURVEY ON THE FUNCTIONING OF ZEP AND THE IWG9

Government Group - survey on ZEP and the IWG9

All Responses

Question 1: Regarding the progress of the SET Plan, do you consider that ZEP has: > The quality of the outputs that are produced under ZEP has been

Question 1 has 5 answers (Radio Buttons)

“Regarding the progress of the SET Plan, do you consider that ZEP has:”

Question 2 has 5 answers (Open Text)

“What is your view on the quality of the outputs produced under the Zero Emissions Platform?”

Unknown contact said:

"They provide a significant move beyond the current state of the art and will reveal future challenges which have a significant impact. Without this some problems/gaps will remain hidden. "

Unknown contact said:

"Gov group meetings and webinars are mostly very informative and useful. "

Unknown contact said:

"The work under ZEP has been good. As none or very little real action has been done, of course everything on ZEP has been on "paper"."

Unknown contact said:

"very good!"

Unknown contact said:

"high quality"

Question 3 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“In what areas could ZEP be improved?”

Unknown contact said:

"Consider hydrogen."

Unknown contact said:

"Even though technical challenges around geological storage are mostly site (reservoir) specific, sharing knowledge of first movers even about negative experiences or project failures may be very useful to the audience. What were the stumbling blocks, how about the learning curve and how did projects progress after major issues. "

Unknown contact said:

"When the real investments starts, then follow those closely."

Question 4 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“What work should ZEP focus on in the future?”

Unknown contact said:

"Hydrogen"

Unknown contact said:

"Mapping out and providing clear solutions for "classic" issues around development of CCS projects like tools to enhance public acceptance (NIMBY) or dealing with hen-egg situations between stakeholders including emitters, project developers and authorities. "

Unknown contact said:

"The same as above, the real investments."

Question 5 has 5 answers (Radio Buttons)

“Regarding the progress of the SET Plan, do you consider that the IWG9 has:”

Question 6 has 4 answers (Open Text)

“What is your view on the quality of the outputs produced under the IWG9?”

Unknown contact said:

"Similar as above, it streamlines the industrial adoption of CCS."

Unknown contact said:

"n.a."

Unknown contact said:

"OK"

Unknown contact said:

"very good!"

Question 7 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“In what areas could the IWG9 be improved?”

Unknown contact said:

"Consider synergies with hydrogen"

Unknown contact said:

"n.a."

Unknown contact said:

"do not know"

Question 8 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“What work should the IWG9 focus on in the future?”

Unknown contact said:

"again, hydrogen together with co2 (cushion)"

Unknown contact said:

"n.a."

Unknown contact said:

"the real investments"

Question 9 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“How could the SET Plan contribute further to national policies and developments?”

Unknown contact said:

"Liaising with policymakers and creating common events. "

Unknown contact said:

"n.a."

Unknown contact said:

"Be active and send the message to the national contacts"

Question 10 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“Would like to be more involved in the SET Plan in the future? In what way?”

Unknown contact said:

"Yes and in any way"

Unknown contact said:

"n.a. "

Unknown contact said:

"I am very much involved with SET Plan, thank you."

Question 11 has 3 answers (Open Text)

“How could the SET Plan/IWG9 be more relevant to national governments?”

Unknown contact said:

"taking into consideration financial incentives"

Unknown contact said:

"n.a. "

Unknown contact said:

"When the investments starts, then practical information, data etc. are more important than visions and potentials."